

CHICKPEA ASCOCHYTA BLIGHT IN BULGARIA

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Abstract: *Ascochyta* blight is the most important disease in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.). The disease is distributed in North, Northeast and Southern regions in Bulgaria. It is caused by the fungus *Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Lab. The pathogen overwintered in plant debris as pseudothecia or pycnidia and in infected seeds as pycnidia. Bulgarian population of *A. rabiei* have high virulence diversity and seven pathotypes distributed in Northeast Bulgaria are identified. Cultural practices and foliar spray are recommended for disease control but in Bulgaria only pyraclostrobin is registered. Bulgarian cultivars Progres and Balkan are reported to be resistant in the past but now Bulgarian population of *A. rabiei* have virulent forms which overcome this resistance. Recently, the farmers used foreign cultivars with unknown reaction to Bulgarian population of the pathogen. This is possible to lead to epiphytotic disease development in years with favorable conditions.

Keywords: Chickpea, *Cicer arietinum*, *Ascochyta* blight, *Ascochyta rabiei*

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Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) is an important food legume which is grown in more than fifty countries and ranks third in the world after common bean and lentil [14]. It is a rich source of good quality protein with ability to sustain soil fertility when included in different cropping systems [23]. The chickpea was not very wide grown legume crop in last twenty years in Bulgaria. In the past three years chickpea fields drastically increased and in 2017 they were 22 564 ha with production 32 383 tones and 59 841 ha with production 58 342 tones in 2018, respectively [48]. The increase in the fields is due to the increased demand on the market, the high cost of production and the subsidies that farmers receive for the production of protein crops.

Biotic stresses play a significant role in increasing losses regarding chickpea production throughout the world [2]. In chickpea, ascochyta blight is the most important disease in many countries [33]. Under favourable conditions as temperature about 20°C and more than 350 mm rainfall during the season yield losses can reach up to 100% [1; 38].

The disease was first reported in 1911 in Pakistan [5]. It infects all aerial parts of the plant. The first symptoms generally seen are small necrotic specks on newer leaves or stems. Under cool, moist conditions, the necrotic specks enlarge and coalesce to form large necrotic lesions (6-12 mm in diameter) on young leaves and buds. Lesions forming on pods and leaves are primarily circular to oval (up to 0.5 cm), containing concentric rings of pycnidia, which are visible with a 10× hand lens. Lesions that form on petioles and stems are usually elongate, but also will contain pycnidia arranged in circular patterns. Stem lesions vary greatly in size, becoming 3 to 4 cm in length, and often girdling stems resulting in breakage. Infected seeds appear small and shriveled with brown discoloration, but may also exhibit irregular cankers [10].

The disease is caused by a fungus which occurs as both teleomorph and anamorph. The teleomorph *Dydimella rabiei* (*Mycosphaerella rabiei* (Kovachevski) v. Arx) was first described occurring in Bulgaria by Kovachevski in 1936 [20]. It is characterized by formation of pseudothecia, a sexual fruiting body containing asci carrying the sexual spores (ascospores). The fungus is a bipolar heterothallic and forms the sexual stage when two compatible mating types (MAT1-1 and MAT1-2) come together [46]. Stanoeva [42] investigated the development of *D. rabiei* in chickpea plant debris in Bulgaria and approved the existence of two compatible mating types in Bulgarian population of *D. rabiei*. In North East Bulgaria mature ascospores occur from the beginning of March till May and this period completely coincides with the chickpea vegetation period that's why ascospores may be primary inoculum for disease development in our country [42]. The anamorph *Ascochyta rabiei* (Pass.) Lab, the asexual or imperfect stage, was first

identified and described by Sattar in 1933 [32]. It is characterized by production of vegetative fruiting body pycnidia containing the asexual spores (conidia). Seed transmission of the disease is possible in Bulgaria [42]. The pathogen overwintered in plant debris on the soil surface as pseudothecia or pycnidia and in infected seeds as pycnidia [20]. Primary disease infection is caused by airborne ascospores or conidia [15]. Once initial infection is established, *A. rabiei* grows asexually on the living host and produces numerous conidia leading to secondary spread of pathogen within the field by rain splash and to some extent by wind [31].

Hosts of *A. rabiei* are species from genus *Cicer* [24]. In Bulgaria, except *C. arietinum*, ascochyta blight development was estimated on *C. montbretii* Jaub. & Spach in Strandzha Mountain [16] which is the only wild *Cicer* sp. native to Bulgaria.

Various terms such as pathogenic groups, races, virulence forms and pathotypes have been proposed as a means to classify the pathogenic variation of *A. rabiei* population on the set of differential chickpea cultivars [6; 17]. Hundreds of races/virulence forms/races are identified worldwide [7, 36, 37, 45] but on the reaction of different differential cultivars: from three [45] to fourteen [13]. At the same time different scales for estimating disease intensity were used with no standard criteria for defining resistance and susceptibility. The nonparametric 1–9 rating scale of Reddy & Singh [29] is the most commonly used method, but it has been employed in different ways by different researchers. All these differences make it impossible to compare the results obtained from different countries, different areas of a country or different researchers. In 2018 Baite and Dubey [4] standardized a set of ten chickpea differential genotypes for race identification and, using 1–9 degree scale, established 7 races of *A. rabiei* in India.

Investigations on virulence diversity in *A. rabiei* in Bulgaria are limited. Stanoeva and Kiryakov [39] investigated the virulence of four *A. rabiei* isolates, originated from Bulgaria, using the fifth differentials proposed by Singh and Reddy [36]. The differential lines showed susceptible phenotype after

inoculation with all isolates which indicated that this set could not discriminate the virulence of the isolates. The authors included in their investigation 42 others introduced lines and their different phenotype after inoculation with the isolates clearly demonstrated differences in the virulence of used isolates. Stanoeva [40] investigated the virulence of 10 monospore isolates, originated from different areas of Bulgaria, to 22 breeding and introduced lines. Although the used accessions were not included in any differential set the results showed high virulence diversity of *A. rabiei* in the country. Stanoeva [43] investigated the virulence of 20 *A. rabiei* isolates on eight differential cultivars proposed by Chongo et al. [7] and identified seven pathotypes distributed in Northeast Bulgaria. Koleva et al. [19] established high virulence diversity of 30 *A. rabiei* isolates on twenty chickpea accessions. According to the authors the 30 *A. rabiei* isolates in their study are different in their virulence from four of the pathotypes identified by Stanoeva [43]. It is impossible to compare the results from investigations which used different isolates and chickpea accessions. Even though Bulgarian population of *A. rabiei* showed high virulence diversity [19, 39, 30, 43] This diversity is probably due to the potential of the pathogen to overwinter in plant debris as pseudotecia [42] and the appearance of different virulent forms/races/pathotypes is a result of recombination during sexual process or due to mutations in the pathogen population which lead to appearance of new more virulent forms. If the standardized set of ten chickpea differential genotypes for race identification proposed by Baite and Dubey [4] domineer in ascochyta blight scientific works then other investigations have to be made to identify race diversity of *A. rabiei* in Bulgaria.

Cultural practices include burning of infected plant residues, deep ploughing, crop rotation, exposure of seeds to direct sun light [15], seed treatment and foliar spray with metalaxyl and captan [14] are recommended for disease control. In Bulgaria only pyraclostrobin is registrated for minimal use by foliar spray [49]. Pyraclostrobin is a strobilurin fungicide

with preventative mode of action. It has translaminar activity but it is not xylem mobile [18]. But chemicals for plant protection are harmful, have residual effects and are expensive as well [47].

So the most efficient, practical, effective and ecofriendly way to manage the disease is using resistant cultivars [12, 22]. Historical studies revealed that ascochyta blight resistance is controlled by a single dominant gene [8], two quantitatively inherited recessive genes and several minor genes [44, 45], multiple recessive genes and a couple of dominant complementary genes [21] and several QTLs have been confirmed with respect to multiple linkage groups against the ascochyta blight resistance [12, 30].

Breeding host resistance against ascochyta blight includes conventional field screening experiments [26] as well as recent molecular breeding techniques [21]. Hundreds of germplasm sources resistant to *A. rabiei* have been reported via field screening methods from 1981 to 2016 [25].

First announcement for resistant germplasm in Bulgaria is made by Ganeva and Matsov in 1977 [9]. The authors reported that accessions Soukhoznyi 14, Kubanskii 199, VIR-32, no. 222, derived from USSR, were highly resistant to Bulgarian population of *A. rabiei*. Radkov [28] determined the resistance in lines no.180 and no.307 to the pathogen. Bulgarian cultivars Balkan and Progress, bred in DAI-General Toshevo, were reported to be resistant to *A. rabiei* under field condition during 2004-2008 [3]. These cultivars are the only ones entered on the Bulgarian official catalogue of varieties of agricultural and vegetable plant species in 2019 [50]. Cultivar Balkan had susceptible phenotype to pathotypes 5, 6 and 7 of *A. rabiei* distributed in Northeast Bulgaria [43]. Balkan and Progress had middle resistant reaction to ascochyta blight under field condition during 2012-2014 and middle resistant phenotype to four and six of thirty *A. rabiei* isolates, respectively in greenhouse [19]. Unfortunately farmers in the country grow foreign chickpea cultivars with unknown reaction to the Bulgarian population of the pathogen. This may lead to

epiphytotic disease development in years with favorable climatic conditions.

The production of resistant genotypes worldwide has become a supreme challenge due to continuous evolving new pathotypes of *A. rabiei* [34]. As mentioned above Bulgarian population of *A. rabiei* showed high virulence diversity and as a result of complex of reasons new, more virulent forms emerge and overcome the resistance of the cultivars. This is the reason systematic screening of the germplasm for ascochyta blight resistance has to be done to find sources of resistance which can be used in a breeding program. Many investigations were carried out and hundreds accessions were screened to many *A. rabiei* isolates but no accession was found with complex resistance to all isolates of the pathogen [17, 39, 40, 41, 42, 43]. If the standardized set of ten chickpea differential genotypes for race identification proposed by Baite and Dubey [4] domineer in ascochyta blight scientific works then other investigations have to be made to identify race diversity of *A. rabiei* in Bulgaria and to screen all chickpea cultivars and lines available in the country to the identified races.

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